

Role of mass m_n in the motion of energy by the flow of time

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(Dated: January 16, 2026)

The role of mass is specified for the motion of energy in the flow of time. In contrast to the massless energy like the light, a mass stays with the present time, and it appears to move to the future from our perspective. A mass plays a role of anchoring the energy to stay in the flow of time. The flow of energy is explained by the the motion of wave that moves along with the flow of time, in which the energy state of the past is always higher than that of the present time. As a result, time always flows from the higher state to the lower state, that is contrary to the motion of wave. The motion of mass is understood by the curved world-line that is made by the light path, by which the center of time axis is deflected from the center of the world-line depending on the mass. It is demonstrated that the gravitational motion of mass is done by its independent motion in the time axis on the curved world-line.

I. INTRODUCTION

On the contrary to the conventional consciousness, the time is not flowing to the future, but it flows to the past, by which the massless wave moves along with the flow of time. With the mass component, the energy is fixed at the present time on the other hand, not moving to the past in the flow of time, which gives a clue why the massless light is not able to stay with the present time.

II. ROLE OF MASS

When it comes to the mass-energy equivalence, it is only considered to be a relation of the mass to the energy, and the motion of wave is derived to explain the decay of particle. However, the genuine meaning of this equation is achieved by substituting the complex energy into the wavefunction. It explains how the energy with a mass can stay at the present time, not flowing to the past. Without the mass, energy is not able to stay at the present time and is followed by the flow of time, and then the energy vanishes in the current time zone, not able to be measured.

With an energy of $E_n^2 = (p_n c)^2 + (m_n c^2)^2$, the mass m_n plays a crucial role in the wave of $\psi_n + \psi_n^*$. The complex wavefunctions are derived by plugging the complex energy $E_n = p_n c + i m_n c^2$ and $E_n^* = p_n c - i m_n c^2$ into the plane wavefunction as shown in the equations of 1 and 2.

$$\begin{aligned}\psi_n &= A_n e^{i \frac{1}{\hbar} p_n (x - ct)} \\ \psi_n^* &= A_n e^{-i \frac{1}{\hbar} p_n (x - ct)},\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

$$\psi_n + \psi_n^* = 2A_n \cos \frac{1}{\hbar} p_n (x - ct), \quad (2)$$

FIG. 1. Contrary to the conventional perspective, the time is supposed to flow to the past, and the energy is anchored by the mass m_n against the flow of time, which makes the energy of m_n stays at the present time.

where m_n and p_n are the mass and momentum components of the energy E_n , and v_n is the speed of the energy E_n , with relations as follows;

$$p_n c = \frac{v_n}{c} E_n \quad \text{and} \quad m_n c^2 = \frac{1}{\gamma} E_n. \quad (3)$$

The energy E_n is supposed to move in the form of $\psi_n + \psi_n^*$, whose amplitude exponentially decreases by $A_n = e^{-\frac{1}{\hbar} m_n c^2 t}$ due to the mass component m_n . By equation 2, $\psi_n + \psi_n^*$ represents the propagating form of the energy through the space and time.

With the mass $m_n \neq 0$, the wave is not able to move along with the flow of time, and it is not supposed to move in the space as well, which implies that the mass plays a role of anchoring the energy to stay counteracting the flow of time, as shown in Fig. 1. It implies that the energy of mass m_n moves to the future from our perspective.

In the equation 1, the momentum p_n comes into play for the energy to move through the space by the flow of time, corresponding to $\cos \frac{1}{\hbar} p_n (x - ct)$, which appears a moving wave of the energy at the speed of light c .

Without the mass by $m_n = 0$, the wave is not suppressed, which indicates that the wave is free to move through the space as the time goes by. It implies that

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FIG. 2. With the time that flows to the past from t_0 to t_{0-} , the world-line is supposed to shift to the past as well, and the light is tracing on the world-line as the time goes by.

the massless energy goes to the past as moving through the space, along with the flow of time.

III. WORLD-LINE

The motion of light can be drawn on the world-line as shown in Fig. 2. From the perspective of A , the speed of light is measured by x_c divided by t_c , and it looks the same regardless the motion of the observer. During the world-line change from t_{0-} to t_0 , light moves from A to C , by which light does not experience the time change at all. For a spaceship moving at the speed of v , it takes Δt during the time t_c , and it looks longer for the observer A who is not moving since the time intervals t_c and $t_c - \Delta t$ should look the same. If the speed of ship reaches the speed of light, the time looks stalled, just for the observer A . For the observer B who is moving experiences the time flow without change, regardless of its speed.

IV. EFFECT OF MASS ON GRAVITY

As shown in Fig. 1, the mass m_n plays a role of resisting against the flow of time that moves to the past. It indicates that the mass holds the energy not to flow along with the time, which depends on each m_n , and it increases for the less mass. Depending on the resisting time, the radius of time axis varies, and it brings mass circle as shown in Fig. 3 (a). By connecting this time to the distance as the mass goes to 0, It becomes the world-line as shown in Fig. 3 (b), and the speed of light is expressed by $\frac{x_c}{t_c}$.

Without the mass, the attenuation factor A_n goes to 1, and the wave of the corresponding energy goes through the space as times passes. Since every object should be placed on this world-line, the time axis of each object including mass must make the right angle on this world-line. By placing the mass circle on the world-line, it creates the time axis oriented to the center of world-line, which makes the center of the mass circle to deflect from the time axis of world-line, refer to Fig. 4.

Since the time goes to the future from our perspective

FIG. 3. (a) Depending on mass, there is supposed to be a mass circle of different time axis. (b) With the time line that is consistent with $m_n = 0$ on the space, it becomes a world-line that the light travels.

FIG. 4. (a) From our perspective, the time flows to the future, the distance d between m_1 and m_2 gets closer by d' as tracing the time axis. Depending on the mass, the mass circle has a different size, and the time axis of each mass circle is not consistent with that of world-line, which brings a gravitation motion of mass. (b) With a flat world-line, there is supposed to be the parallel time axis regardless of the mass, and it brings no gravitational motion of mass at all.

that is opposite to the direction of time, the flow of time is equivalent to move the world-line to the direction of time. By tracing the flow of time at each point on the world-line, it can be observed that the distance d between m_1 and m_2 decreases by d' as shown in Fig. 4 (a). With masses m_1 and m_2 , the mass circle is smaller than that of world-line, and the direction of time axis of mass is not consistent with that of world-line. Since the time axis of the mass should be consistent with that of world-line, it brings the time axis of mass move towards the center of world-line, which appears a motion of mass to each other.

With a flat world-line that is equivalent to the infinite speed of light, it brings a parallel time axis regardless of the mass, and no gravitational motion of mass by the time, which implies that the gravity is made by the finite speed of light, as shown in Fig. 4 (b).

When it comes to the gravity, it can be understood by the mass circle that brings a inconsistent time axis depending on the mass m_n , by which the wave of energy E_n is suppressed by the attenuation factor A_n . By following the time axis of mass circle on the world-line, it brings a decrease of distance on the world-line, and it makes a mass of a small mass circle to move to other mass as the time goes on.

It implies that the gravitational motion of mass is not

FIG. 5. Wave is supposed to move along with the flow of time, from the present to the past. The time appears to flow from the past to the present with respect to us, and then time appears to flow from the higher energy state to the lower state.

made by between masses that is believed to make a space-time curvature around mass, but each energy of mass m_n just moves independently due to its mass circle on the world-line.

V. ENERGY STATE WITH FLOW OF TIME

When it comes to the entropy, it is explained by the flow of energy, which insists that the time flows from the higher energy state to the lower state by the flow of time. My approach is different from this.

Contrary to conventional perspective, it can be understood by the motion of wave that moves from the present t_0 to the past t_{0-} following the flow of time as shown in Fig. 5. The wave $\psi_n + \psi_n^*$ always moves from the present time t_0 to the past t_{0-} along with the flow of time, not going in the forward direction from the past to the present, which indicates that the state of energy in the past is always greater than that of present.

From our perspective, time looks to move in the forward direction, from the past to the present. As a result, time appears to flow from the higher energy state to the lower state from our perspective, which is opposite direction of the wave that moves from the present to the

past.

The flow of time is explained by the motion of wave with respect to the energy whether it has a mass m_n or not. By seeing the motion of wave compared to the flow of time, it is evident that the state of energy moves from the higher to the lower state over the time from our perspective.

VI. SUMMARY

The conventional view looks the time to flow to the future, and mass and light also are considered to move to the future along with the flow of time. From this perspective, the flow of time is not determined, and every motion of the nature should be reversed symmetrically with respect to the time.

However, it is not the story, time flows to the past, and a wave of the massless energy is supposed to follow the flow of time as propagating through the space as time goes by. Due to the mass, the motion of wave is suppressed in the time axis, which is denoted by A_n for each energy with mass m_n . Owing to this suppression, the energy of mass can stay with present time, not swift away to the past.

With the world-line that is made by the light path, the time axis on the world-line makes a right angle at every position on the world-line, and every time axis is supposed to meet at the center of world-line. Following this time axis to the flow of time, a distance on the world-line is supposed to shrink down to meet, which is the source of the gravitational motion by the time. With a mass that creates a mass circle that is smaller than that of world-line, time-axis of this mass circle is deflected from the center of world-line, and it makes the mass falls down to each other. By following the time axis of each mass m_n , it can be observed that the distance between masses decreases as time goes by. The gravitational motion is made by the independent motion of mass that traces on its own time axis, not an interaction between massive objects. The massless energy disappears from the present time. With a mass component m_n , the motion of wave resists against the flow of time, and the massive energy stays with the current time. It appears to move to the future from our perspective.